

Analytical Utility of the Interaction between Chloranil and Electron Donors

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Molecular interactions between chloranil and electron donors will lead to the formation of many types of the reaction products, such as outer complex, inner complex, radical ions and substitution products. Analytical utility of such formations in solution are presented and discussed.

CHLORANIL (2,3,5,6-tetrachloro-1,4-benzoquinone) is one of the familiar quinonoid with all the four positions substituted by electron withdrawing chlorine atoms and hence will act as a good electron acceptor¹. Its electron affinity is reported to be 1.37 eV on Briegleb's relative affinity scale² and is sufficiently high. The postulation of the inter-molecular charge transfer theory by Mulliken^{3,4} in electron donor-acceptor system, has evinced a good interest among the scientists and many workers studied chloranil as an exemplary acceptor. Several reviews have been published on the electron donor-acceptor systems and those by Briegleb⁵, Rose⁶, Foster⁷, Rao⁸, Yarwood⁹, Gutmann¹⁰ and Butufei¹¹ are considered to be important on the charge transfer interaction of chloranil with electron donors¹².

The molecular interaction between electron donors and chloranil are generally classified into two types of reactions: the first type includes the formation of a weak charge transfer complex (also known as outer complex or π complex) with little or no further reaction¹³⁻¹⁶, and the second type includes the nucleophilic substitution reaction either *via* outer and inner complexes as intermediates^{17,18} or outer complexes and ionic species as intermediates^{19,20}. Either of the reaction paths listed above will depend mostly on the electron donor characteristics, concentration of the donor, temperature, polarity and dielectric constant of the solvent medium.

The interaction of chloranil with electron donors leading to the molecular complexes and substitution products in solution is reported to be useful for the identification and determination of donor substances. Various such reports for the analysis of compounds, familiar as organic, medicinal and biochemicals, are compiled and discussed in the present paper. In addition, methods for the detection and estimation of chloranil, based on the nucleophilic substitution reaction are also presented.

The formation of charge transfer complexes finds use in the spot detection and chromatographic identification of substances, based on their electron

donor property. Few reviews appear in literature²¹⁻²³ on this aspect. Recently, we have reviewed the use of the charge transfer complexes for the analysis of pharmaceuticals and dosage forms²⁴. The reports on the use of chloranil as reagent for the analytical purpose are listed in Table 1.

The charge transfer complexes of chloranil have a definite ratio and orientation with the electron donors. Almost all the chloranil complexes possess intense colours and absorb in the visible region⁶⁻¹². Identification of donors on tlc using chloranil as spray reagent is thus feasible. The development of colours on a spot plate is also useful for the simple visual detection of substances at microgram level.

The property of the complexes, absorbing the radiation in the visible region, is made use of for the quantitative determination of the donor substances by spectrophotometry. The methods of determination are just simple and consist of just addition of chloranil to the donor, and measurement of the molar absorptivity at particular analytical wavelength. The equilibrium constants of the chloranil complexes are considerable in many cases and are moderately high, when alicyclic amines serve as donors^{55,56}.

The charge transfer complexes of chloranil formed are associated with reasonable time stability. Though not often, they are reported to be stable for more than a day^{14,22-27}. Excess concentrations of chloranil appear to be a primary condition for the time stability of the charge transfer complexes. The complexes of chloranil are generally found to be moderately polar¹², and as such moderately polar solvents, like toluene, ethyl acetate, dichloromethane, chloroform, acetonitrile and methanol may be considered to be suitable as solvents for the purpose. However, alcohols, ethers, esters and water are not recommended as solvents for chloranil^{24,26} as they are known to form complexes. Among the other solvents chloroform is found to be useful for the extraction of donor substances. Further, the limit of saturation of

chloranil in chloroform is about 7×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, the highest concentration of chloranil that can be achieved in any organic solvent. Thus chloroform is recommended as the best solvent for the studies with chloranil.

Elevated temperature may increase the rate of complex formation⁵⁶, but the molar absorptivity of the complexes formed between quinones and amine donors is found to have non-consistent decrease by 0.7 to 2.8%. The decomposition

TABLE 1—IDENTIFICATION AND DETERMINATION OF COMPOUNDS USING CHLORANIL AS REAGENT

Method	Compd. determined	Solvent medium	Ref.
Detection of pink to brown colour on spot plate	Aromatic primary and secondary amines, amino acids and phenols	Dioxane	25
Chromogenic detection and mass spectrometric identification	Aniline and phenol derivatives, related fungicides and metabolites	Chloroform, acetone	26
Detection of colour on spot plate : pink	Anesthesin, streptocide white, othazol and norsulphazole	Aqueous alcohols	27
green colour	Ephedrine, mezatol, nanophyn, chloridine, arecoline, novocaine, novocainamid, pachycarpine, savcaine, spasmolytin and spherophysine	Aqueous alcohols	27
blue green	Amisyl, dinezin, diprazine, condelphin, thicaine and triethylamine	Aqueous alcohols	27
red	Salsolidine, salsoline, atropine, nicotinic acid, polycarpine and ptalyphylline	Aqueous alcohols	27
blue	Diethylamine and piperazine	Aqueous alcohols	27
Spot detection of blue colour	Piperidine and piperazine	Chloroform	14
Detection on tile plate with chloranil as spray reagent	3,4-Methylenedioxyphenol and its derivatives	Benzene	28
	Pyrrole, carbazole, indoles, indolecarboxylic acids, indole aldehydes and tryptophan	Acetone, chloroform	29
	Pyrrolizidine alkaloids like pipavarine, brucine, harmaline, synphylline and lycopsanine	Toluene, methylene, chloride	30
	Alkaloids like strychnine	Ethanol	31
Spectrophotometric measurement of the charge transfer complex	Piperidine and piperazine	Chloroform	14
	Morpholine	Chloroform	32
	Thiomorpholine	Chloroform	33
	Penicillin G sodium, naphthazoline, chemizole, and piperazine	Dioxane	34
	Piperazine and its salts	Ethanol	35
	Piperazine, its salts and dosage forms	Chloroform	36
	Chlorpromazine, promethazine, promazine, perphenazine, chlorprothirene, opipramol, amitriptyline, imipramine and hydroxyzine	Dioxane ethanol	37
	Isonicotyl-, nicotinoyl- and picoinoyl-hydrazines	Water, pH 9	38
	Carboxylic acid and homologues and their salts	Dimethylformamide	39
	Pyrrole, indole, carbazole, norharmaline, harmaline, harmine and harmaline	Chloroform	40

(Table 1 contd.)

Spectrophotometric measurement of the final substitution product	Ammonium salts and tertiary amines	Toluene	41
	Primary aromatic amines	Water, pH 9	43
	Primary aliphatic amines and aniline homologues	Water, pH 9	44
	Aromatic amines, proteins, ammonium salts and semicarbazide	Water, pH 9	45
	Benzaldoxime and its 4-hydroxy, methyl, chloro and nitro derivatives	Water, pH 9	46
	Chlorpromazine	Water, pH 9	47
	Enamines of acetals, ethers, esters, aldehydes and ketones	Dimethylformamide	48
	Carboxylic acids and their salts	Dimethylformamide	49
	Alanine, glycine, valine, leucine, arginine, cystine, cysteine, proline, tyrosine, histidine and other amino acids	Water, pH 9	50
	Nitrilotriacetic acid, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid and homologues, amino acids and peptides	Aqueous ethanol	51
	Tranexamic acid and its dosage forms	Water, pH 9	52
	Primary, secondary and tertiary amines, both aliphatic and aromatic	Dioxane, propylalcohol	53
	Piperazine and its salts	Aqueous alkaline solutions	54

of the complex formed perhaps is the probable reason.

In most of the complexes, the composition is found to be 1:1, donor to chloranil. However, as mentioned earlier, excess concentrations of chloranil will keep the complex stable. In excess concentrations of the donor, the interaction of chloranil will generally lead to the nucleophilic substitution reaction, except in case of some π -donors. The degree of substitution is found to be two in most of the cases. With the exception of tertiary aromatic amines^{19,20}, the substitution reaction will proceed through outer and inner complexes as reaction intermediates²⁷. The formation of final substitution product also in some cases is reported to be useful for the analysis of the donor substances as listed in Table 1.

Although some colour reactions are reported to be useful for the detection of chloranil on spot plates^{28,29}, it is our first effort to bring out a simple spectrophotometric method for the quantitative determination of chloranil^{60,61}. In excess concentrations of the electron donor like piperidine, the outer complex formed between chloranil and donor transforms to disubstitution product in solutions of chloroform⁶². The concentration of the product is found to vary linearly with quinone with the condition of keeping the donor a large excess. The final product is also stable, if protected from light. In stoppered bottles reproducible absorbances are measured even after two days. The method also tolerates a wide variation in the donor concentration and is found to be sensitive to 3 μ g of chloranil per ml.

Other amines which are useful for the purpose are 2,3- and 4-methylpiperidines⁶¹, 2,6- and 3,5-dimethylpiperidines⁶¹, morpholine^{62,63}, thiomorpholine⁶³, 1-methylpiperazine and piperazine⁶³. All these reagents for chloranil are alicyclic secondary amines. Other amines used for the determination of parent benzoquinone, such as diethanolamine⁶⁴, aminoantipyrine⁶⁵ and methylamine⁶⁶ are also useful for the determination of chloranil, but the conversion of quinone to diaminoquinone is relatively slow, when compared to the cyclic aliphatic secondary amines.

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